

USE OF MODERN TECHNOLOGIES USED TO IMPLEMENT 3-D MODELING
FROM BIOLOGY AS A FACTOR FOR DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS' RESEARCH
COMPETENCES

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Abstract. *At the modern stage of technological development, designers, architects, physicists, biologists and others widely use the possibilities of 3D technology in their projects and developments, scientific research activities. Naturally, this innovation did not bypass the educational sphere and the educational process. The use of elements of 3D modeling technology in biology classes improves the practical training of schoolchildren, which leads to successful acquisition of technical specialties. The activity of creating computer models not only deepens students' spatial imagination, but also helps to develop their intellectual and creative abilities in the field of modeling.*

Keywords: *possibilities of 3D technology, elements of 3D modeling technology, Virtual existence technologies, designers, architects, physicists, biologists, "Artificial existence", development of students' research competencies.*

Virtual reality technologies have long been successfully used to support decisions, including government decisions, but it should be noted that the interpretation of the term "virtual reality" is not generally accepted. Often this term is used to refer to three-dimensional computer models of reality. In *A Critical History of Computer Graphics and Animation*, W. Carlson, J. Briggs, and S. Bryson define virtual reality as a "dimensional computer simulation" and "the use of computer technology to create the effect of an interactive three-dimensional world." riffs, respectively. Bryson's definition is very close to the definition of "virtual reality" by J. Lanier, who is considered the author of the term, who understands virtual reality and emphasizes that an environment in which the user can work in real time is created with the help of a software computer complex. In 1986, Doe mentioned that this term was used for the first time in the discussion of the research of S. Fischer, who was working on the problem of "virtual environment" ("Virtual environment") at that time. Thus, this term used to be an alternative to M. Kruger's "Artificial Being" and W. Gibson's "Gibspace".

At the modern stage of technological development, designers, architects, physicists, biologists and others widely use the possibilities of 3D technology in their projects and developments, scientific research activities. Naturally, this innovation did not bypass the educational sphere and the educational process.

3D-modeling is one of the common directions of using information and communication technologies, and not only experts, but also new users are engaged in this work. Any modern multimedia program cannot be implemented without computer graphics. The tasks before students are interesting and often difficult to solve, which requires increasing learning motivation, developing logical thinking, using their abilities in computer science and determining the connection with biological science, and using their creative abilities. .

Management of 3D technology programs allows a student of any level to actively participate in the educational and cognitive process and to demonstrate their thoughts at a high level: lessons are at a high level of complexity, including questions that are interesting and understandable for everyone. can be transferred.

The use of elements of 3D modeling technology in biology classes improves the practical training of schoolchildren, which leads to successful acquisition of technical specialties. The activity of creating computer models not only deepens students' spatial imagination, but also helps to develop their intellectual and creative abilities in the field of modeling.

Computer 3D-modeling in biology is distinguished by its wide range of possibilities, it makes high use of its interdisciplinary connections with mathematics, physics and other sciences. In order to have a complete scientific worldview, to develop their creative abilities, to become a specialist who will meet the demand in the future, it is necessary for students to thoroughly master the basics of 3D modeling on a computer, and to apply the knowledge they have acquired in their educational activities.

Studying 3D modeling as part of the development of students' professional competences is a creative task of the teacher and includes the use of many pedagogical technologies in the educational process:

- the use of problem-based educational technology helps students acquire knowledge, skills and abilities that develop mental abilities;

- differentiated educational technology, strong students confirm their creative abilities, weak students have the opportunity to achieve academic success, and the level of professional search increases;

- design technology enables the development of individual creative abilities of students, a conscious approach to professional and social self-determination;

- the research method allows students to independently supplement their knowledge, deeply study the problem being studied and propose ways to solve it, which is important in forming a worldview. This is important for determining the individual development path of each student.

To organize the educational process, information technologies are used, which have a significant impact on the nature and organization of the educational process, because the nature of the interaction between the student and the teacher has changed, and part of the pedagogical functions have been transferred to the computer. will be held.

Without methodological training and didactic materials, it is impossible to effectively conduct training with the help of 3D-modeling, because the coverage of those who want to engage in modeling is almost the majority, and their level of training is also different. The presence of detailed instructions for the completion of assigned educational tasks for each student allows you to effectively "load" according to his ability and the speed of learning the material.

Each student can show his personality. Individual, group and face-to-face forms of work are used in this experience: lecture, practical work, creative project, educational game, competition, subject-related exercises.

Assignments using the elements of 3D technologies are planned to be conducted independently in extracurricular activities. Assignments are designed for students of different levels of training.

Practical tasks in the 3D program are creative with reference to the elements of spatial modeling. Such activities include the use of the following methods: synchronous work of students on computers, tasks to strengthen their knowledge, test their skills, online mastering of school materials by students; necessary for planning independent work tasks, organizing and coordinating students' cognitive activities on the computer.

When studying topics using 3D technology in biology classes, students make more complex changes in the organism. The work is organized in the form of a group, which allows almost every student to prove his success in discussions, collaborative decision-making, adjusting the level of knowledge on the subject, developing the ability to work independently, and demonstrating leadership and managerial qualities.

In the course of practical work, group members have the opportunity to present their assumptions about how to model events and processes, how to solve problems that arise, and evaluate their strengths. In addition, group activities allow to gain experience in communication, to have the ability to prove one's point of view, which is important in the formation of students' information competences.

The priority form of work that helps in the formation of basic competencies is the project method, the purpose of which is to provide students with the opportunity to learn independently in the process of solving problems and assignments that require the integration of knowledge from various disciplines. This technology allows students to make the process of acquiring knowledge more interesting due to the ability to solve tasks using previously acquired knowledge and skills, to express themselves in practical independent activities. It is better to leave the choice of tools and methods of problem solving to the students themselves. This leads to the creation of a state of success and guidance in education and career.

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